

was grown during the normal rice-growing season. The nematode population was monitored during the maximum tillering stage of rice by the methods described previously.

The results indicated that May solarization significantly reduced nema-

Farming systems

Deepwater rice establishment in boro rice in the flood-prone ecosystem of West Bengal, India

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In flood-prone deepwater rice (DWR)-growing areas of West Bengal, India, cultivating boro (dry season) rice has become common during the past 10-12 yr. Boro rice is usually transplanted in January and harvested between the end of April and mid-May. The standing boro crop, however, interferes with seeding wet season DWR in April/May. As a result, DWR sowing is either delayed or abandoned. The grain yield of boro rice is an assured 4-5 t/ha compared with an uncertain yield of 1-1.5 t/ha for DWR. So farmers grow boro rice and sacrifice growing DWR.

However, innovative farmers have started to grow both boro and DWR by adjusting the establishment technique. This method was developed in the Moyna Basin, a perpetually flood-prone deepwater area of Midnapore District, West Bengal. It comprises 4,000 ha of land connected with the Kangsabati River through a channel. The whole area lies below the river bed, consequently rain and floodwater collect and remain stagnant except for a short time in April/May. Maximum water depth in the basin center is 100-130 cm during August/September. Boro rice is planted after stagnant flood water is pumped through the channel in January.

We surveyed and interviewed 14 farmers in three villages during 1993. Their practices can be summarized as follows:

tode population compared with non-solarized plots (see table), whereas November solarization did not. This may be because in May, the temperature was high enough to kill the nematodes but it was not in November. May solarization of ricefields may be an effective strategy

- Boro rice varieties IET826, IET1444, and IR36 are sown in seedbeds in late November/early December.
- Land is prepared for transplanting boro seedlings, which includes applying diammonium phosphate @ 200 kg/ha and muriate of potash @ 70 kg/ha.
- Freshly harvested (Nov-Dec) seeds of photoperiod-sensitive traditional DWR varieties, such as Hatipajra, Amol, Raktapanikalash, and Kamouth, are broadcast at 70-90 kg/ha and incorporated into the soil during puddling for the boro season crop. They remain dormant for a considerable time.
- Boro seedlings (45-50 d) are transplanted in mid-January and urea at 140 kg/ha is applied at 30 and 60 d after transplanting.

Farm machinery

Seeder developed for direct sowing of rice under the puddled soil surface

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Farmers in South and Southeast Asia are rapidly adapting wet direct sowing as a labor-saving technology for rice crop establishment. A drum seeder was developed at IRRI for direct row sowing of pregerminated seeds on the surface of puddled soil. When this practice is used, sown seeds are likely to be eaten by birds and rats or desiccated in the dry parts of the field. The seeder cannot be operated in the rain as seeds sown in a line would be dispersed. These unfavorable conditions constrain the adoption of the drum seeder by some farmers.

It was found recently that pregerminated seeds can be sown under the

for reducing the initial inoculum of the rice root nematode in areas where it is a problem. ■

- Mature boro rice is harvested by the end of April, after which the soil starts to crack.
- With the onset of premonsoon rain, germinated DWR seedlings start to appear 30-35 d after the boro harvest.
- DWR germination rate is usually 60-70%. Seedlings are 20-25 cm tall with 1-2 tillers/plant after 1 mo—when the flood waters start to accumulate.
- Urea at 70 kg/ha is applied 45 d after the seedlings appear to improve their growth.
- DWR yields range from 1.0 to 1.8 t/ha depending on the severity of the flood.

This establishment method for DWR in boro rice allows farmers to harvest 5-6.8 t/ha of rice per year, with DWR contributing 25-36% of the total yield. ■

puddled soil surface (anaerobic seeding), where sown seeds are protected from bird and rat damage, rain splashing, and desiccation. To overcome the constraints to adoption of the drum seeder, we developed an anaerobic seeder. The drum seeder was modified with spring-loaded furrow openers and closers, rotary flotation drive wheels that prevent the unit from sinking in fields with deep plow layers, and a detachable rainguard, which prevents the seeds from getting wet, thus clogging the drum (see figure). The unit weighs 10 kg. Production cost in the Philippines is US\$150. Row spacing is adjustable. The seeding rate was determined by the number of holes around the drum, seed size (a cultivar trait), and the germination conditions.

The seeder was tested with five rice cultivars (see table). The seeding rate varied from 38 kg/ha (IR41996-50-2-1-3, seed weight 27.7 mg/seed) to 80 kg/ha (BG34-8, 22.6 mg/seed). Seedling

Anaerobic seeder designed to put rice seeds under the puddled soil surface. Positions of drum and furrow openers and closers are adjustable. The rainguard is attached to the lifting bar. Abbreviations: cc = center to center distance, ϕ = diameter.

Performance of 5 rice cultivars sown by anaerobic seeder.^a IRRI, Philippines. 1994 dry season.

Cultivar	Seeding rate ^b		Crop establishment ^c		Sowing depth ^d (mm)	Grain yield ^e (t/ha)
	(no./m ²)	(kg/ha)	Seedling (no./m ²)	Establishment (%)		
BG34-8	354	80	285 a	81 ab	7.1 a	5.4 a
IR41996-50-2-1-3	136	38	135 b	99 a	5.3 a	5.2 a
IR72	172	41	129 b	75 b	5.0 a	4.8 a
E4129	238	59	152 b	64 b	3.8 a	3.9 b
AUS351	206	46	141 b	68 b	4.9 a	3.0 c

^aRandomized complete block design with four replications. Means having a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. Fertilizer was applied at 50, 30, and 50 kg N/ha at 21 and 42 d after sowing and heading, respectively. ^bEstimated by measuring the weights of seeds loaded into the seeder and left in the seeder after sowing. Calculation of number of seeds sown was based on the weight of single seed. Mean of four plots of replications. ^cMeasured 3 wk after sowing. ^dEstimated by measuring the length between seed and the portion of leaf sheath where the color changes from white to green. The 20 plants sampled for the measurement of crop establishment were used. ^eHarvest area = 6 m².

establishment ranged from 64 to 99%. Sowing depth was 4-7 mm. Grain yield varied from 3.0 t/ha (due to lodging) to 5.4 t/ha.

The ease with which seeding rate and row spacing may be changed will be useful for the agronomic studies of direct seeding. No seeder currently available is as flexible and as easy to operate as this one. The seeder might be useful for farmers shifting from transplanting to direct sowing. The blueprint is available free of charge from IRRI. ■

A low-cost chopper for farm byproduct use

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When farm byproducts such as rice straw, cane tops, and corn stover are chopped, they can be used for livestock feed, mulch, compost, green manure, and handmade paper. By converting these "farm wastes" into useful products, wasteful burning may be minimized, and farmers may realize additional income.

We have developed and tested a portable, low-cost (\$250), inclined-axis chopper that is easy and safe to use (Fig. 1). It makes use of locally available materials, fabrication skills, and equipment.

The blades were made from leaf spring. The four rotating blades were angled 10° upward with respect to the stationary counterblade for effective and low-power cutting (Fig. 2). The angled blades also function as a centrifugal fan to throw the presented materials effectively when chopped. Both the rotating blades and counterblades are reversible to avoid frequent sharpening.

To reduce costs, we excluded any feeding device, which ensures convenient feeding and controlled length of chop. Two compensating features were instead included: a blade configuration for suction-assisted feeding, and a 45° inclined blade housing with a hopper perpendicular to it for easy gravity

feeding. With these features, the materials need not be pushed, but simply thrown or dropped into the hopper. This ensures the safety of the operator's hands and prevents him or her from stooping. The floor of the housing functions as a simple regulator by restricting length of introduced materials to 25 mm.

The prototype was tested with napier grass (70.9 and 80.9% MC, wet basis [wb]), corn stalks (62.7% MC, wb), rice straw (47.9 and 65.9% MC, wb), and sesbania (newly cut, 82.0% MC, wb). The power requirement, capacity, and specific energy were determined for each of these materials at four speeds (900, 1050, 1200, and 1500 rpm) and with a set clearance for each. Power requirement